

Effects of textile dyes (in waste water) on vegetation

Ayesha Ali^{*1}

¹Department of Soil & Environmental Science, Muhammad Nawaz Shareef University of Agriculture, Multan

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7459824

Received: Jan 01, 2022	Published: June 27, 2022	Volume: 1	Issue: 1	Pages: 5-6
------------------------	--------------------------	-----------	----------	------------

Pakistan's economy can be classified as semi-industrialized as a developing country (GOP, 1991), contributing around 24% of the country's gross domestic product (GDP). Textiles are a vital industry in Pakistan's industrial sector, and they play an essential role. Pakistan is Asia's eighth-largest exporter of textile items. Textile processing units generate an estimated 1,441,167m of wastewater per day. The untreated discharge of this effluent has not only harmed the quality of drinking water but has also added pollutants to the environment (soil and water).

While rapid industrialization has brought comfort to humankind, it has also harmed the environment. It can be seen that advances in industrialization over the last few years have increased emissions of pollutants into the environment. Textile wastewater contains high concentrations of contaminants, including total dissolved solids (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), and a variety of other organic and inorganic chemicals (heavy metals). In the composition of most of the residual waters of the textile industry, there are relatively high levels of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD), total dissolved solids (TDS), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP) and non-biodegradable organic compounds; all collectively make the textile effluent highly toxic. However, the concern is that the presence of these hazardous chemicals limits its use for

irrigation. When directly flowing in the fields, Textile wastewater clogs the pores of the soil, resulting in loss of soil productivity and inhibiting plant growth.

Dye wastewater has become one of the most dangerous forms of pollution due to the rising demand for textile products and the corresponding expansion in the manufacturing and application of synthetic dyes. The textile industry's direct environmental impacts are those caused by the discharge of untreated effluents into water bodies, which typically account for 80 percent of the industry's overall emissions.

Several dyes are used for colouring, with a few being classed as reactive, direct, basic, and acidic. The most popular cationic dyes are azo basic anthraquinone dispersion dyes. Because of their high-water solubility, they are difficult to remove using typical methods. The dyes listed below have negative effects on the plants employed in the dyeing process by industries:

Azo Dyes:

Azo dyes are widely used in the textile industry because of the ease and cost-effectiveness of their synthesis and the greatest variety of colors. These azo dyes have been discovered to be complicated in nature and to have carcinogenic evidence on reductive cleavage. In about 15-50 percent of cases, Azo-type textile dyes do not bind to the fabric during the dyeing process and are discharged into the wastewater for agricultural irrigation. The use of these azo compounds

* Correspondence: aishaali.2625@gmail.com

is very harmful to soil microbial communities and plants' germination and growth.

These dyes have the potential to change the physical and chemical qualities of soil, degrade water bodies, and affect the environment's flora and fauna. The poisonous nature of dyes has been discovered to induce the death of soil microorganisms, which impacts agricultural output.

The Basic Red 9 Dye:

Basic Red 9 dye, used in the textile, leather, paper, and ink industries, has carcinogenic potential and is very harmful to the environment. It degrades into carcinogenic aromatic amines under anaerobic conditions, and their disposal in water bodies can cause allergic dermatitis, skin irritation, mutations, and cancer. The Basic Red 9 dye effluents may adversely influence some plants' growth when water is used for irrigation purposes.

Sudan I Dye:

Sudan I (also commonly known as CI Solvent Yellow 14 and Solvent Orange R) is an organic compound. The Sudan I, also commonly known as CI Solvent Yellow 14, contains Cl; when the untreated wastewater is discharged directly into the environment, the accumulation of the chloride in the soil can cause acute toxic effects on the soil. However, high levels of chloride can have adverse effects on an ecosystem. Chloride may impact freshwater creatures and plants by affecting reproductive rates, increasing species mortality, and altering the ecosystem's overall features. Furthermore, chloride can stress plant respiration and alter the quality of our drinking water as it filters down to the water table.

Textile effluents are undesirable, and treatment is essential not only for environmental reasons but also for reuse. Therefore, it is essential to use treatment strategies to ensure the sustainability of the environment for future generations through physical, chemical, and biological technologies or a combination of them.

Phytoremediation is an environment-friendly plant-based approach involving plants to extract and remove elemental pollutants from the environment or reduce their bioavailability in soil.

Phytoremediation can be understood as the ability of plants to degrade, extract, transform and detoxify the contaminants of the air, soil, sediments, surface water, and groundwater. The phytoremediation of textile dyes is environmentally correct, economically efficient. However, it takes a long time than standard bioremediation processes as the plants need time to grow and absorb the hazardous materials from the brownfield.

Despite the excellent results, all bioremediations offer limitations to a greater or lesser degree. However, molecular biology, genetic engineering, and nanotechnology, coupled with academic-scientific research, can overcome these constraints and act as great tools to promote sustainable development to the present and the future.